

Effect of Hemolytic Substances on Red Blood Corpuscles and the Mechanism of Hemolysis.

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A large number of workers have studied the hemolysis of red blood corpuscles by different substances (see Hober, *Physikalische Chemie der Zelle und Gewebe*, 1924, p. 499) but as yet no clear explanation exists as to the mechanism of the change in the permeability of the stroma or the corpuscle membrane under the influence of different hemolytes. That a single explanation may not cover all cases is evident from the fact that simply pure water will hemolyse the corpuscles which is entirely due to the absorption of water owing to a difference in the osmotic pressure inside and outside the cell membrane. The membrane is thus ruptured owing to a swelling of the whole cell. While conducting some experiments on the hemolysis of red blood corpuscles by hemolytes, the attention of the authors was drawn to the problem from a different point of view, namely, what effect each individual constituent of the cell has on the properties of the other constituents. Consequently the stability of hemoglobin, lecithin, cholesterol and albumin, which are known to be the chief constituents of the cells, in presence of each other has been investigated, and in this paper a preliminary account of these researches is given.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The hemoglobin sol was prepared by digesting 5 grams of Merck's pure hemoglobin in about 400 c.c. of water for an hour and then filtered. The filtrate was then made up to 500 c.c. The cholesterol suspension was prepared by dissolving about 0.5 gram of the substance (Kahlbaum) in alcohol and then pouring into 500 c.c. of water. The suspension obtained was then filtered. The lecithin sol was prepared by allowing 10 grams of Merck's pure lecithin (nach ova) to imbibe some water for 24 hours, and then emulsifying in 500 c.c. of water. The egg-albumin was a crystalline variety obtained from Kahlbaum and was dissolved in water and used without any further

dialysis. Of the different hemolytic agents, saponin was obtained from British Drug Houses, Ltd., sodium taurocholate and glycocholate from Merck and potassium oleate from Kahlbaum. The taurocholate and glycocholate were prepared only a few hours before they were used, as these salt solutions were very liable to decomposition at the temperature of the laboratory, about 87°F. The hemoglobin sol and the albumin sol did not also keep well, a bacterial decomposition setting in after a few days.

The first series of experiments were done to determine the stability of the hemoglobin suspension in presence of various other substances. The experimental method consisted in taking 5 c.c. of the sol and mixing it with a 5 c.c. solution containing an electrolyte and the substance whose effect was under investigation. The total volume was always kept 10 c.c. The electrolyte concentration is expressed in moles per litre of the reaction mixture, unless otherwise stated.

From Table I it will be observed that alcohols greatly sensitise the hemoglobin suspension towards BaCl₂. With potassium chloride also similar result was obtained. With pure alcohols (up to 60 per cent.) however there was no precipitation of the hemoglobin.

TABLE I.

Effect of Methyl and Ethyl Alcohol.

BaCl ₂ ,	'001	'001	'001	'001
Methyl or ethyl alcohol in c.c.	0	1	2	3
Time in minutes				
0	no effect	slightly turbid	turbid	very turbid
15	do.	do.	ppt.	ppt.
25	do.	do.	ppt.	ppt.
40	do.	strongly turbid	no settling	precipitate settles.

These results agree with those of Jirgensons (*Kolloid Zeit.* 1927, **41**, 331; **42**, 59). In Table II the effect of saponin is shown. The saponin concentration is expressed in grams per 10 c.c. of the reaction mixture,

TABLE II.

BaCl ₂	'001	'001	'001	'001
Saponin	0	'025	'05	'075
Time in minutes				
0	no effect	immediate turbidity.	immediate ppt.	immediate ppt.
5	do.	does not settle	settles slowly	settles almost immediate
20	do.	do.	complete settling.	complete settling.

From this table it will be observed that saponin considerably sensitises a hemoglobin sol. On further experimentation an interesting fact appeared. The saponin when dissolved in water, itself coagulated the hemoglobin when added in sufficient concentration. When a trace of acid was added to the saponin solution, the precipitation of hemoglobin was very rapid, but in presence of a slight amount of alkali, saponin had no precipitating effect. In Table III the effect of lecithin on hemoglobin is shown.

TABLE III.

BaCl ₂	'001	'001	'001	'001
Lecithin (c.c.)	0	'5	1'0	1'5
Time (minutes)				
0	no effect	turbid	turbid	turbid
15	do.	slight ppt.	ppt.	ppt.
25	do.	do.	do.	do.

From Table III it will appear that a lecithin sol sensitises the hemoglobin considerably. In alkaline solution however no sensitisation could be observed. The importance of keeping blood alkaline in normal health is thus obvious. In Table IV the effect of egg albumin is shown.

TABLE IV.

BaCl ₂	'001	'001	'001	'001
Albumin 1.5% in c.c.	0	.5	1.0	1.5
Time				
5'	no effect	slight ppt.	ppt.	ppt.
15'	do.	do.	do.	do.

Table IV shows that albumin also sensitises the hemoglobin sol towards BaCl₂. The effect of cholesterol was also studied, but probably due to the very small concentration of the sol, no effect was observed. In Tables V to VIII the effect of saponin, lecithin, albumin and potassium oleate on hemoglobin sol towards potassium chloride is shown.

TABLE V.

KCl	'08	'08	'08
Saponin	0	'025	'05
Time			
0	no effect	turbid	turbid
8'	do.	do.	do.
18'	slightly turbid	do.	settles
30'	turbid	do.	do.
50'	ppt.	settles	do.

TABLE VI.

KCl	'08	'08	'08
Lecithin	0	.5	1.0
Time			
0	no effect	turbid	turbid
7'	do	do	do
15'	do	do	ppt.

TABLE VII.

KCl	'08	'08	'08
Pot. oleate 2½% c.c.	0	'5	1'0
Time			
0	no effect	no effect	no effect
18'	slightly turbid	do	do
50'	ppt.	do	do
95'	ppt.	do	do

TABLE VIII.

KCl	'08	'08	'08
Albumin	0	'5	1'0
Time			
0	no effect	no effect	no effect
5'	do	turbid	turbid
18'	do	do	do
15'	do	do	ppt.

From these results it will be observed that so far as albumin, lecithin and saponin are concerned, the results are quite similar to that obtained with $BaCl_2$. In the case of potassium oleate however, which could not be tested with $BaCl_2$, owing to a precipitating effect, the results are exactly opposite, namely potassium oleate has a marked peptising effect on the hemoglobin. In connection with these experiments the effect of a bile salt, namely sodium taurocholate was also examined. It was found that this salt has also a distinct though small peptising effect. In Tables IX and X the effect of the mixtures $BaCl_2 + KCl$, $BaCl_2 + KOH$ and $KCl + KOH$ are shown.

TABLE IX.

BaCl ₂ M/100 c.c.	1·6	1·6	1·6
KCl M/5 c.c.	0	1·0	2·0
Time			
30'	turbid	no effect	turbid
60'	do	do	do
BaCl ₂ c.c.	1·8	1·8	1·0
KCl c.c.	0	·5	1·0
Time			
30'	turbid	turbid	turbid
BaCl ₂ c.c.	2·2	2·2	2·2
KCl c.c.	0	1·0	2·0
Time			
0	turbid	no effect	no effect
7'	do	turbid	turbid

TABLE X.

BaCl ₂ M/5 c.c.	·5	·5	0	·0
KCl M/5 c.c.	0	0	4·0	4·0
KOH final concentration.	0	M/100	0	M/100
Time				
30'	ppt.	no effect	ppt.	no effect

From the results presented in Tables IX and X it will be observed that there is a distinct though small antagonistic action between

BaCl₂ and KCl in certain concentrations. With mixtures containing KOH however the antagonistic action is very great, and with greater amounts of KOH the hemoglobin sol could not be flocculated even with a large amount of BaCl₂.

So far only the experimental results with barium and potassium chlorides have been given. Experiments were also made with heavy metal cations such as silver, mercury and uranium and the results are substantially the same. Hence these are not given.

Experiments with Lecithin Sol.

In the foregoing pages a number of results have been given on the stability of hemoglobin in presence of various substances. In Tables XI to XV the effect of hemoglobin on lecithin is shown. The experiments have been done exactly in the same way as before. Five c.c. of the lecithin sol was taken and the total volume was 10 c.c.

TABLE XI.

BaCl ₂ , M/5 in c.c.	.2	.2	.2	.2	.2
Hemoglobin in c.c.	0	.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
Time					
5'	no effect	ppt.	no effect	no effect	no effect
17'	do	do	do	do	do
35'	do	do	ppt.	do	do
50'	do	do	ppt.	do	do

TABLE XII.

BaCl ₂ , M/5	.3	.3	.3	.3
Hemoglobin	0	0.5	1.0	1.5
Time				
0	no effect	ppt.	no effect	no effect
5'	do	do	do	do
15'	do	do	ppt.	do
30'	do	do	ppt.	do

TABLE XIII.

BaCl, M/5	1·0	1·0	1·0	1·0
Hemoglobin	0	0·5	1·0	1·5
Time				
2'	ppt.	ppt.	ppt.	ppt.
5'	do	do	do	do

TABLE XIV.

HgCl ₂ , M/25 in c.c.	·5	·5	·5	·5
Hemoglobin	0	0·5	1·0	1·5
Time				
0	no effect	no effect	ppt.	ppt.
15'	do	do	do	do
25'	do	do	not clear at the top.	clear at the top.
145'	do	do	clear	clear

TABLE XV.

AgNO ₃ , M/5 in c.c.	·2	·2	·2	·2
Hemoglobin	0	·5	1·0	1·5
Time				
0	no effect	slight ppt.	ppt.	ppt.
10'	do	ppt.	do	do
120'	ppt.	top not clear	clear	clear

The results given in Tables XI to XV show that with heavy metal salts the hemoglobin has a sensitising action at all the concentrations, but with low amount of barium chloride a distinct maximum

of the sensitising action occurs at a certain concentration of the hemoglobin. This is very similar to the effect of albumin on a ferric hydroxide sol as observed by Brossa and Freundlich (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 306). A further study of this point is being made. It is of importance to note in these cases that the hydrophobic sol of hemoglobin distinctly sensitises the hydrophilic sol of lecithin towards metal cations. Hence the original membrane formation may be in part due to a slow precipitation of the lipoids owing to the sensitising action of the albuminoids present.

There are two other constituents of the cell membrane which require investigation, namely cholesterol and protein. The presence of protein as a membrane constituent is very probable but not yet proved. Hence it is not known what the protein is. The experiments conducted with egg albumin plus lecithin in presence of barium and potassium salts have not been decisive as to whether the lecithin is sensitised or not. It is however known that lecithin has an agglutination maxima in a markedly acid region of the hydrogen ion concentration, whereas in presence of albumin this point is shifted towards more-neutral region. Also albumin-lecithin mixtures give a sharper flocculation point and forms coarser flakes. (Feinschmidt, *Biochem. Zeit.*, 1912, 38, 244). It is also known that in some cases neutral albumin gives a precipitation with cholesterol. So far as heavy metals are concerned, the ordinary albumin gives a precipitate with them, and lecithin is also sensitised towards these salts.

With regard to cholesterol, the phenomenon is much simpler. Cholesterol in water gives a hydrophobic sol, and the addition of lecithin considerably stabilises it. A mixture of lecithin and cholesterol acts like a hydrophilic sol (*cf.* Porges and Neubauer, *Biochem. Zeit.*, 1907, 7, 152; Rona and Deutsch, *ibid.*, 1926, 171, 89). This however, does not necessarily mean that the membrane also behaves like a hydrophile, for the protein would be denatured in the process of membrane formation and hence would give hydrophobic properties to the membrane. The results of Gough (*loc. cit.*) on the agglutinating power of different cations on red blood corpuscles support this (*cf.* however Mines, *Kolloid Chem. Beihefte.* 1912, 3, 226). As a matter of fact the precipitation or the peptisation of the membrane to be discussed later on appears to be practically irreversible, and hence points to its being more hydrophobic than hydrophilic.

Two further experiments with lecithin will now be given, namely the effects of saponin and sodium taurocholate on the stability of lecithin sols. A few words are however necessary beforehand to show their importance.

It is well known that saponin and bile salts are excellent hemolytic agents, and hemolyse the red blood corpuscles rapidly. It has all along been supposed that their action is entirely on the membrane materials. Thus a solution of the bile salts has apparently a dissolving effect on lecithin and cholesterol and several compounds of lecithin and bile salts have been described in the literature (*cf.* C. H. Boehringer Sohn; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1924, ii, 1515; also Long and Gephart, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 30, 1812). Fraser and Gardner (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1909, B, 81, 230) consider that saponin combines with cholesterol. Though no compound formation of lecithin with saponin has yet been reported, yet the action of this substance has also been considered by Bayliss (*General Physiology*, 1918, p. 133) to be similar to that of bile salts. It is of interest therefore to study whether they have any peptising effect on lecithin sols. The following two tables give the results:—

TABLE XVI.

BaCl ₂ M/5 in c.c.	.5	.5	.5	.5
saponin in grams.	0	.025	.05	.075
Time 0	no effect	no effect	no effect	no effect
10'	ppt.	slight ppt.	do	do
20'	ppt.	turbid	do	do
25'	ppt.	very turbid	less turbid	least turbid

TABLE XVII.

BaCl ₂ M/5	.5	.5
Sodium taurocholate 1% in c.c.	0	1.0
Time 0	no effect	no effect
10'	ppt.	do
20'	ppt.	do

These results show definitely that lecithin is peptised by saponin and taurocholate. Thus it is possible that the so-called solution of lecithin in bile salts is nothing but a peptisation phenomenon. Consequently it is quite probable that the hemolysis of red blood corpuscles is due to a peptisation of the membrane. It is however, known that both saponin and bile salt hemolysis is inhibited by normal serum. Hence the question naturally arises as to the nature of this antagonistic action, and some investigation has been carried on this point. But before proceeding further a short literature on the subject is given.

It is known from a long time that normal serum inhibits the hemolytic action of saponin and bile salts. Ransom (*Deutsch Med. Woch.*, 1901, p. 194) observed that cholesterol inhibits the action of saponin, and he attributed the inhibitory effect of serum to its cholesterol content. The inhibitory effect of serum on the action of bile salts was studied by Bayer (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1907, 368). It was found by him that cholesterol has no inhibitory effect, that lecithin produces inhibition but not in quantities that occur in blood, and that the proteins of the blood are responsible for the inhibition. In this connection mention may be made of the observations of Von Eisler (*Zeit. f. Exper. Path. u. Ther.*, 1906, 3, 296) who stated that serum globulin inhibits the action of Staphalolysin and Tetanolysin, and also those of Liebermann (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1907, 4, 25) who found that hemolysis by soaps is prevented by serum albumin. Bayer's researches have in the main been confirmed by Sellards (*Bull. of John Hopkins Hospital*, 1908, 19, 268). In recent years Ponder (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, B, 95, 42; and Kennedy, *Biochem. J.* 1926, 20, 237) has investigated the inhibitory effect of sera, sugars etc., and has given some interesting conclusions. No one has, it seems, tried to find out whether any relation exists between the amount of hemolyte and the inhibitor in the case of bile salts. Since this inhibitory effect of various substances are important in the study of the permeability relations of the membranes, some experimenets were conducted on the hemolysis of blood corpuscles and the results will be given now.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the experiments given in the following pages, defibrinated and washed sheep's corpuscles, completely freed from serum by repeated centrifuging with normal saline was used. The R.B.C. was suspended in physiological saline. The solution of serum was prepared in the

same saline in the dilution of 1:10. The egg protein was obtained from a fresh egg and similarly diluted. Neither of the natural proteins were dialysed nor the globulin was separated. The solutions of the bile salts were also made in normal saline and were M/20 strong. In actual experiment 2 c.c. of a 5% suspension of the R.B.C. was taken in a test tube, and in another test tube, known amount of the bile salt solution was mixed with a known amount of serum and calculated amount of normal saline was added to it to bring the combined volume of the R.B.C. suspension and the bile salt solution when mixed together to a standard volume of 10 c.c. The contents of the two tubes were rapidly mixed three times and then allowed to rest in a stand. In majority of the experiments an arbitrary time of 12 minutes was given for complete hemolysis to take place which was determined visually by comparing with a standard hemolysed tube as is usually done in the case of Wassermann reaction. By varying the quantity of the bile salt added, the exact amounts of either glycocholate or taurocholate which would hemolyse completely the 2 c.c. of the suspension in presence of known amounts of serum in 12 minutes were determined. When sufficient care was taken to use always sterilised flasks, test tubes and pipettes the results were quite reproducible. The experiments were done at the laboratory temperature of 87-88° F, but the R.B.C. suspension when not in use was always kept in an ice chest.

In Table XVIII some data are given of the inhibitory effect of normal serum on glycocholate and taurocholate hemolysis. The object was to make a comparative study of the hemolytic powers of these two salts. As far as the authors are aware, this has not been done by any previous investigator. The study would be interesting however, because in the bile excretions the amount of glycocholate is almost double that of taurocholate.

TABLE XVIII.

R. B. C. = 2 c.c. Total volume=10 c.c.

Amount of normal serum added c.c.	Time in minutes required for complete hemolysis in presence of	
	Na glycocholate M/20 1 c.c.	Na taurocholate M/20 1 c.c.
0.00	1	42
0.05	2	...
0.10	4	92
0.20	12	Partial hemolysis only after 2½ hours.
0.30	30	
0.40	69	

The above data show quite conclusively that glycocholate has a much greater hemolytic power than the taurocholate even in the presence of blood serum. The inhibitory power of the serum in very small quantities may also be noted. These facts are important in certain pathological cases such as in jaundice where there is a great secretion of bile salts which are absorbed in the blood stream. The inhibitory action of the serum counteracts the abnormal hemolysis which would otherwise occur due to the excess of glycocholate secreted. In Tables XIX and XX we have summarised the quantitative data on the inhibition of glycocholate hemolysis by means of serum and egg protein.

TABLE XIX.

R. B. C. = 2 c.c. Time for complete hemolysis = 12 minutes.

Amount of normal serum added in c.c.	Amount of glycocholate reqd. in grams.	Amount of glycocholate neutralised per unit quantity of the serum.
0.0	0.01096	...
0.1	.02435	0.1339
0.2	.04870	.1887
0.3	.07305	.2069
0.4	.09009	.1978
0.5	.11201	.2021
0.6	.13392	.2049

TABLE XX.

Amount of egg protein in c.c.	Amount of glycocholate reqd. in grams.	Amount of glycocholate neutralised per unit quantity of egg protein.
0.0	0.01096	...
0.1	.02678	0.1582
0.2	.05087	.2495
0.3	.08522	.2475
0.4	.10230	.2283
0.5	.12905	.2362
0.6	.14610	.2252

The amount of glycocholate neutralised per unit quantity of the inhibiting substance which has been given in the third column of the above tables has been calculated as follows: Taking for example the data with 0.5 c.c. serum, the excess of glycocholate necessary for hemolysis in presence of this amount of serum is 0.11201—0.01096 grams and hence the amount of glycocholate neutralised per unit quantity of the serum is $(0.11201 - 0.01096)/0.5$ gms. Other data have also been obtained in a similar way. The results show the peculiar fact that with both the inhibiting substances, the amount of the hemolysing substance neutralised per unit of the inhibiting substance is almost constant, though the value of the constant differs in the two cases. Rejecting the first data, the mean value of the constant in the case of normal serum is 0.20008 and in the case of egg protein is 0.2373. Egg protein has thus a much greater inhibiting effect than normal serum. The constancy of the ratio points to some sort of chemical interaction between the bile salt and the proteins. It is not known however whether the ratio will remain constant with even greater quantities of the serum, but experiments are in progress. Ponder (*loc. cit.*) has observed in the case of saponin that the quantity of the hemolysing substance neutralised per unit of serum decreases with increase in the concentration of the serum. This points to an adsorption effect of the surface. The data obtained by us are not in variance with this hypothesis, as in many so-called chemical adsorptions such as with gelatine or chrome tanning, a similar thing happens with low concentrations.

These facts naturally raise the important question of the nature of the action exerted by the inhibitory substances like proteins on the hemolysis of the R. B. C. It has already been stated that Brossa and Freundlich (*loc. cit.*) found that albumin sensitises a ferric hydroxide sol, and according to Brossa (*Kolloid Zeit.*, 1923, 32, 107) serum globulin considerably sensitises negatively charged sols of congo red and benzo-purpurin. Reznikoff (*J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1922, 8, 92) observed that serum albumin has a distinct precipitating effect on colloidal gold in certain concentrations. A similar sensitisation was found by Fischer and Fodor (*Kolloid Zeit.*, 1923, 32, 279) of colloidal gold in alkaline globulin solution. Reitstötter (*Zeit. f. Immunitätsforsch.*, 1920, 30, 507) has found that albumins from various sera strongly sensitise many sols. Michaelis and Rona (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1907, 2, 219; 3, 109; 4, 11; 5, 365; 1908, 7, 329; 8, 356; 14, 476) have shown that sols of ferric hydroxide, mastic

emulsion or kaolin suspension can be sensitised by natural protein solutions. In this class belongs the sensitisation of suspensions of bacteria by blood plasma of pregnant women (Löwenthal and Berthau, *Zentrabl. f. Bakteriolog. u. Parasitenkunde*, 1919, I Abt. **83**, 315; Vorschütz, *Pflüg. Archiv.*, 1921, **186**, 290). In all these cases the sensitisation is due to the adsorption of the proteins on the surface of the colloids. The assumption is therefore justifiable that in the case of blood corpuscles also the action of normal serum is one of sensitisation of the colloidal membrane. Inside the body this sensitising action is not evident probably owing to the presence of other hydrophilic colloids like fibrinogen, etc. It is interesting at this place to draw an analogy with an inorganic sol. The agglutinating power of different cations are according to Gough in the case of sheep's R. B. C. in the order $Ce > Th > Ca > K_4Fe(CN)_6$, whilst the coagulating powers of these cations on a copper ferrocyanide sol as determined by us is $Ce > Th > Ca > K_4Fe(CN)_6$, beginning with the highest. Copper ferrocyanide further offers a closer analogy in that it forms membranes with properties very similar to those of the stroma. Thus it is impermeable to sugars and to many metal salts at low concentrations, which is quite analogous to the behaviour shown by the stroma. A recent investigation by Gurchot (*Jour. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 83) has shown that the variable permeability of the copper ferrocyanide membrane in presence of different substances is caused by the coagulation or the peptisation of the membrane, and he has drawn attention to the fact that the change in permeability of many plant cells in presence of alcohols investigated by Czapek (*Ber. Deutsch. Bot. Ges.*, 1910, **28**, 159) and the results of Walden (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1893, **10**, 699) with different organic acids is nothing but due to a coagulation of the membranes. If now a similar view is advanced to explain the permeability of the stroma, the following becomes obvious. We can consider that ordinarily the membrane is in the peptised condition and consists of a fine granular particles the interspaces of which are filled in by the adsorbed aqueous medium, an assumption exactly analogous to that of the copper ferrocyanide membrane. Hence water and many water soluble substances can pass through the membrane. Aqueous solutions of some neutral salts are however not easily permeable because the stroma is polarised owing to the existence of an electrical charge. Salts which have a high coagulative power on the stroma may make the membrane permeable but at the same

time the hemoglobin may be precipitated, whilst those with a comparatively lower coagulating power will be permeable only at high concentrations. This may be the explanation of the fact that the R. B. C. is not permeable to sodium or potassium ions. That with low concentrations of strongly coagulating ions a permanent change occurs in the stroma is shown by the results of Mikwa (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1924, 149, 550) who found that small amounts of uranyl acetate actually damage the structure of the cells as is shown by the increased sensitiveness to physiological saline. The impermeability of the sugars is however due to a different cause namely due to negative adsorption, a fact well known in the case of copper ferrocyanide membranes. Assuming then that the hemoglobin does not take any part in the process, hemolysis depends on the following several factors :—

- (1) Actual coagulation whereby the membrane material will form coarse flakes, and hence form cracks or holes.
- (2) Complete peptisation whereby the whole membrane will get loosened, each particle getting separated from the other.
- (3) Mechanical or other form of rupture, such as due to swelling or imbibing of water either by the cell as a whole or by any component of the membrane.
- (4) Pure solubility effect, as for example in the case of some organic solvents.

Leaving aside the fourth case for the present, it is clear that the other facts will be dependent on the colloidal condition of the membrane. Thus the effect of blood serum is to protect the membrane from easy peptisability by sensitising it. It has however no actual flocculating action, otherwise hemolysis would occur. The hemolysis by heterologous sera is probably an example in which a new body is present having hemolytic properties. When an actual coagulation takes place, the hemolysis will be evident unless the coagulant is strong enough to coagulate the hemoglobin itself (*cf. Mond, Pflüger's Archiv*, 1925, 208, 574). Thus in the case of mercury salt the following results were obtained with horse blood (*cf. Lepeschkin, Med. K. Vet. Nobelinstitut*, 1924, 6, 1),

	Time in minutes	5	15	25	35
(·0001 % HgCl ₂ ,	% hemolysed	0	30	80	100

Dunin-Borkowski (*Bull. Acad. Sci., Cracow*, 1908, 494) however

observed that a higher concentration of mercuric chloride than that required to produce complete hemolysis agglutinates the erythrocytes. The behaviour of other heavy metals are of a similar nature.

The acid or alkali hemolysis offers some interesting points. Since the membrane is slightly negatively charged in normal saline, the first action will be to lower the charge, and the lecithin-protein complex will get precipitated. With higher concentration of the acid, the hemoglobin will also be acted on, increasing in size with a consequent change of colour towards brown. The lecithin may also be decomposed with the liberation of fatty acids. In equal concentration, greater action will be exerted by an acid whose ionisation constant is greater. The following data with horse blood (*cf. Lepeschkin, loc. cit.*) show the results.

TABLE XXI.

HCl in moles per litre	Time in minutes	5	20	35	120	1000	Colour of hemoglobin.
*0008	% hemolysis	7	10	10	10	10	red
*0010	do.	21	30	30	30	30	red
*0100	do.	80	100	brown

Acetic acid	Time	5	30	40	50	100	1000	colour of hemoglobin.
*0010	% hemolysis	1	2	4	4	4	4	red
*0017	do	11	38	45	45	45	45	red
*0036	do	40	95	100	red
*0100	do	80	100	red

From the above results it will be evident that HCl has a greater effect than acetic acid. With regard to the effect of alkali, the first action of it will be to peptise the membrane slightly and thus increase its stability. With higher concentration however the protein portion of the membrane will be dissolved forming salts of the type sodium albuminate, and hence the membrane will become ruptured liberating the hemoglobin (*cf. Arrhenius and Madsen, Zeit. physikal. Chem., 1903, 44, 7*). In this connection the researches of Eggerth and Mond may be mentioned. Thus Eggerth (*J. Gen.*

Physiol., 1924, 6, 587) found that when washed sheep's corpuscle is suspended in solutions of p_H 5.2 or more acid, it becomes progressively more electropositive, and this change is coincident with hemolysis. In investigating the hemolytic power of H^+ and OH^- ions, Mond (*Pflug. Archiv*, 1925, 208, 574) found that a slight decrease in p_H from neutrality causes hemolysis, but on the alkaline side of the neutral point, there is a wide zone of resistance.

The hemolytic action of soaps are also of the same nature as those of the bile salts. These substances also lower the surface tension of water and has a great peptising effect on the membrane materials. Another great similarity of the membranes with that of copper ferrocyanide arises here. Thus it is known from previous researches that sugars sensitise a sol of copper ferrocyanide (Sen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 517). Hence they may be expected to have a similar action on the corpuscle membrane, and hence there ought to be an antagonism between peptising hemolytic agents and sugars. This has actually been observed by Ponder and Kennedy (*loc. cit.*) with a large number of sugars and saponin. These facts, therefore, lead us to the view that *the inhibiting effect of proteins or sugars on saponin, soap or bile salt hemolysis is only a special case of the antagonistic action between a sensitising and a peptising agent in diphasic systems well-known in colloids, biochemistry and physiology* (Sen, *Kolloid Zeit.*, 1926, 39, 324; Clowes, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1915, 20, 407; Lillie, *Am. J. Physiol.*, 1912, 29, 372; Osterhout, *Plant World*, 1913, 16, 129; *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1914, 19, 335).

In conclusion it may be stated that two types of hemolysis have not been discussed, namely by narcotics and by bacteria. So far as narcotics like chloroform, ether, etc., are concerned, it is usually believed that they dissolve the lipoids, but according to Loewe (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1912, 42, 297) lecithins, kephalins and related substances give colloidal solutions in choloform, petroleum ether and other solvents. Porges and Neubauer (*Kolloid Zeit.*, 1909, 5, 193) have pointed out that the precipitation of lecithin in ethyl alcohol solution by $CdCl_2$ and other salts have many points of similarity with a coagulation by electrolyte, and that the ethereal solution also has properties which may be interpreted on the assumption of colloidal solution. Consequently it is quite possible that with narcotics also, the hemolysis is due to an extreme peptisation of the membrane constituents.

So far as bacterial hemolysis is concerned, the work on Staphalysin and Tetanolysin has been mentioned. Some work has been done by the present authors also, but it is as yet incomplete. It appears however that bacterial hemolysis is a form of destruction of the membrane due at first to a liquefaction of the solid membrane particles and subsequent decomposition of the protein portion. As a matter of fact it appears that the protein constituent is the first thing to be attacked by the bacterias. The phenomenon seems to be analogous to the liquefaction of gelatine gels by many bacilli. The subject will be discussed in a future paper.

Summary.

(1) Hemoglobin forms a negatively charged sol in water. Acids sensitise and alkali peptises the sol. Towards electrolytes it behaves like a typical hydrophobic sol.

(2) Hemoglobin sol is sensitised by alcohols, lecithin, albumin and saponin. In alkaline solution however lecithin does not sensitise the sol. Mixtures like barium chloride and caustic potash and potassium chloride and caustic potash have a considerable antagonistic action. A slight antagonism is also observed with the mixture barium chloride and potassium chloride. Saponin precipitates the sol in slightly acid medium, but not in alkaline medium. Potassium oleate considerably stabilises it towards potassium chloride. Sodium taurocholate has also a slight peptising action.

(3) The lecithin sol behaves like a hydrophilic colloid. With heavy metal salts, hemoglobin has a sensitising action at all concentrations, but with barium chloride, a maximum effect has been observed beyond which the hemoglobin has a peptising action.

(4) Lecithin sol has a strong stabilising action on cholesterol suspensions.

(5) Saponin and the bile salts peptise lecithin. Cholesterol is also peptised by the bile salts.

(6) An experimental study has been made on the inhibitory effect of blood serum and egg protein on glycocholate and taurocholate hemolysis of sheep's R.B.C. It is shown that this effect is only a special case of the antagonistic action between a sensitising and a peptising agent in diphasic systems.

(7) It has been found that glycocholate is a much stronger hemolysing agent than taurocholate.

(8) The mechanism of hemolysis of red blood corpuscles by hemolytes has been discussed. It is shown that the membrane is in the colloidal state, and hemolysis may occur either due to an extreme coagulation whereby cracks will be formed, or due to an extreme peptisation whereby all the particles will go into apparent solution thereby loosening the whole structure. In some cases it may be due to a pure osmotic effect where a mechanical rupture of the membrane is possible. This view will explain the following cases:—Hemolysis by hypotonic solutions, by heavy metals, by saponin, soap and bile salts, by narcotics and possibly that by bactericidal action.

It is not however the intention of the present authors to suggest that hemolysis is entirely a colloidal phenomenon, but it is quite probable that in certain cases an ordinary chemical effect such as a scission of the fatty material from the kaphalins by the action of, say acids, may be of determining influence. Also in the case of cobra venom, along with a peptising effect, a fermentative action possibly takes place.

The experiments with the red blood corpuscles were made in the Bacteriological Department of the Bactro-Clinical Laboratory Ltd., Calcutta, and our best thanks are due to the authorities for the free gift of all the necessary materials.

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